

Interrelation of Blood in Urine with Use of Sleeping Pills

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ABSTRACT

If someone is using sleeping pills regularly there are more chances of blood in urine. The purposes of the up to date study were to confirm how urine blood interrelated with sleeping pills use. Different people worked in this project and all were belongs to university peoples. Majority people have evocative to use of inactive drugs but they deny recognizing it. Mostly people utilize sleeping pills.

Keywords: *Sleeping pills, Urine blood.*

1. Introduction

The another name of the blood in urine called Hematuria. Hematuria is the health check phrase for red blood cells in the urine. Red blood cells in the urine preserve approach from the kidney. The urinary region includes the ureters, the bladder, the prostate in men, and the urethra. There are two types of the hematuria Gross hematuria or Microscopic hematuria. There is no specific treatment of the blood in urine.

Sleeping pills is more world widely used all over the world. Sleeping pills is used to reduce stress, pain or insomnia. Mostly people who are suffering from psychological problems are called sedative.

Emazepam is the most common used drug in the world. If someone is using sleeping pills regularly there are more chances of blood in urine. The scientific workers have already been correlate different parameters to this specific topic [1-5]. Principle of this study was to confirm how urine blood interrelated with sleeping pills use.

2. Materials and Methods

First of all take the sample of the urine which contains blood. Urine tests offer reason about the source of hematuria. It may comprise a urinalysis, which is performed with a measuring rod test and occasionally use a microscope to investigate the filling of the urine. A unusual test that may be performed is a urine cytology, which uses a microscope to evaluate cells from the inside layer of the bladder and kidney.

There are different test to determine te cause of blood in urine like CT scan, Ultrasound etc.

Study Design

A opinion poll was structured to confirm how urine blood interrelated with sleeping pills use. Different peoples have different views about the use of inactive drugs.

Arithmetical Investigation

Theme created by resources of Microsoft Office and M state.

3. Results and Discussions

The values of the how urine blood interrelated with sleeping pills use is given as table 1. Males with 55% use sleeping pills while males with 44% dislike sleeping pills. Females with 54% use sleeping pills while females with 46% dislike sleeping pills.

Table 1. How urine blood interrelated with sleeping pills use

Gender	Sleeping pills use	Aversion to sleeping pills
Male	55%	44%
Female	54%	46%

4. Conclusion

It was concluded that mostly people exploit sleeping pills.

Declarations

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

The authors are willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

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